

CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR TO ONLINE SHOPPING: A STUDY ON PRIVATE UNIVERSITY STUDENTS OF BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Nowadays, Technology has evolved online shopping to become a thriving business. In this industry, Bangladesh has enormous potential. This study aims to understand how the global web has influenced people's attitudes and behaviors. In this study, the descriptive method is utilized to get quick responses from the respondents. In the present study, a non-probabilistic sampling method was used to collect data from the private universities around Dhaka and other divisions. We identified 500 students and conducted personal interviews with them, and 430 of them responded to the survey, yielding a 90% response rate. Ordinal regression analysis has been used to measure the effect of some independent variables on consumer buying behavior. We found that age groups "26-30" and "31-35," specific income ranges, and sources of information such as "Promotional Campaigns" and "Social Media" play a significant role in influencing the outcome. Moreover, better assistance and concentrating on improved client experience to expand.

Keywords: Consumer; Behavior; Online Shopping; E-Commerce; University Students; Bangladesh.

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite the consumers continuing to shop from a physical store, the consumer feels convenient for online shopping refers to purchasing goods or services from a website or mobile application using the internet. Online shopping is a straightforward resolution for a busy life in the modern world. It is a structure of Electronic Commerce. Online shopping is a recovery of an urgent time for contemporary people because they get so bustling that they can't or are reluctant to spend plentiful time looking. The market has around 147 billion Bangladeshi Taka products listed for sale online. In the past decade, there has been a colossal amendment within the approach that customers are searching for. The appearance of the web and the increasing sophistication of communication technology of the twenty-first century have made nearly every facet of our lives simple and cozy. Online shopping is a process whereby customers directly

buy goods or services from a seller in real-time, without an intermediary service, over the Internet Trees & Stewart 2000. The current standard of E-commerce in the People's Republic of Bangladesh is one step before the initial stage of electronic banking, electronic price tickets, restricted services of mobile banking, and virtual looking area units are conducted online. The zoom of the world net population and the adoption of ICT in numerous sectors have reshaped the approach of communication and demand, utilizing its potential to the event of trade and commerce. Advancement is all but inevitable.

Consequently, this study is to confront customer conduct towards online shopping, their inclination, detesting, and fulfillment elevation. In the 21st century, trade and commerce have so spread that multichannel has taken place, and online shopping has accumulated considerably throughout the planet (Johnson, Gustafsson, Andreessen, Lervik, & Cha, 2001). In Bangladesh, online shopping has been developing speedily and has the dormant to fill dramatically to return, as web scattering come to many wide across the open country. Notwithstanding, it's furthermore a fact that the Bangladeshi people's region is generally conventionalist in their way of dealing with looking in the light of modernization and quick life; reliance on online looking can increase. Like different youthful Asian social orders, youngsters in the Bangladesh region are exploring particular avenues regarding new ways of shopping that have contributed to the acknowledgment and development of online thorough searching in Bangladesh. Positively, customers become continuously familiar with the web and its benefits. Online shopping is transforming far and wide and getting inclination among a noisy group of customers looking for considerable cost recommendations connecting with data, comfort, cost, and decision. Globally, e-commerce has implanted about a pair of.29 trillion-dollar market (John, 2018) and is expected to achieve four trillion dollars by 2020 (eMarketer, 2016) because of the double-digit worldwide growth in sales (15%) and order (13%) (eMarketer, 2018) all told varieties of e-commerce like business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) (Zuroni & Goh, 2012). Additionally, the paper has been designed to find the means towards client fulfillment, as their aptitude drives them for that. This report has the probability of helping the specialists concerning the appalling subject of client aptitude. Additionally, this investigation has found how much client assumptions and conduct concerning internet business stores. The inquiry has many aspects. Through this examination, we've acquired a few expected information about the

client's skills concerning online shopping, the issues and boundaries, and the method for beating them. This study explores the impact of social aspects on customers' purchase intentions when buying online, specifically about the quality of items purchased. It explores the variety of goods and services available on various websites, including transportation tickets and expenses. The research also investigates how consumers' attitudes toward online purchasing may differ, focusing on the issue of customers' perceptions of online purchasing.

This study is an attempt to organize and summarize the literature about online marketing and enlighten the research routes that will contribute to the advancement of the discipline. The study has several aims to investigate the deliberate usage of the internet and population statistics for Bangladesh. It also illustrates the benefits of online shopping and discusses the current online shopping policies or e-commerce of the Bangladesh Government. Furthermore, the study analyzes the behavior of people in online shopping in Bangladesh. Finally, we go for ordinal regression analysis to measure the effect of some variables on consumer buying behavior.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Globally, Globally, online shopping is progressively growing in popularity. This virtual mechanism influences customers' tastes and preferences of their purchasing behavior. This study aims to identify the variables influencing private university students in Bangladeshi online shopping behavior, a growing global phenomenon that impacts customers' tastes, preferences, and purchasing habits.

Rodgers and Harris; Citrin et al., 2003, Online shopping is less socially acceptable for women in contrasted traditional stores, as it requires more tactile input for product appraisal. Men's preference for convenience and social connection hurts online purchases, especially for tactile items like shoes, according to Swaminathan et al. (1999).

Kanchan, Kumar, and Gupta (2015) found that shoppers aged 30-45 are more interested in online purchasing than other age groups. Consumer requirements, interests, and attitudes differ with age, and younger consumers are more favorable toward innovation (Darian 1987; Modahl 2000; Rogers 2003; Steenkamp; Wotruba and Pribova 1996). According to Khare, Khare, and Singh (2012), the age of Indian consumers influences their online shopping behavior. Diverse era of shoppers have diverse opinions toward internet purchasing (Bhatt, 2019). Consumer purchasing behaviors are changing and may alter with age (Qazzafi, 2020).

Abul Kashem and Jebun Nesa Alo, 2021: Bangladesh Bank has announced a new payment method for e-commerce companies, requiring customers to approve the transfer fund. The commerce ministry plans to send a letter to the central bank, and financial institutions will not be allowed to transfer money without customers' consent. The new system requires digital outlets to invest in new customers and handle delivery failures under the Consumers' Rights Protection Act and the ICT Act. Non-bank financial institutions warn customers about risky transactions with e-commerce merchants.

Consumers with higher salaries or who are wealthier have greater purchasing power. Sharma and Parmar (2018) discovered that consumers with higher and intermediate incomes buy more things online than those with lower incomes. In this study, they identify that people with considerable incomes purchase online more frequently.

Mahmud and Hossain's 2014 study reveals that website reliability, design, customer service, and competency are key factors influencing online purchase attitudes. Ma and Ma (2012) found that factors such as perceived safety, website structure, costs, and product quality significantly influence university students' online purchasing attitudes.

Jukariya and Singhvi (2018) and Dani Dani (2017) explored factors influencing MPUAT and Udaipur students' online purchasing motivations. Key factor includes lower prices, discounts, feedback, product quality, transaction security, personal privacy, product pricing, access speed, and after-sales support.

Frandsen, M. (2016), Marketing professionals have recognized the impact of social media on personalized sections, purchasing experiences, convenience, and vast information searches. Dabbous A. 2020 Recent studies show significant outcomes, with Ewing M., 2019, indicating that referring products on social media increases purchase likelihood by 71%.

Fatema and Siddiqui, 2021; Rahman and Rahman, 2020; Neger and Uddin, 2020; Islam, 2017; Rahman et al., 2018. This study aims to identify factors influencing online purchase intention among Bangladeshi private university students and uses a logit link function, filling a gap in the literature and improving understanding of online purchasing despite the numerous studies on the subject.

3. INTERNET USAGE AND POPULATION STATISTICS

YEAR	Users	Population	% Pen.	GDP p.c.*
2000	100,000	134,824,000	0.1 %	N/A
2007	450,000	137,493,990	0.3 %	US\$ 466
2009	556,000	156,050,883	0.4 %	US\$ 574
2010	617,300	158,065,841	0.4 %	US\$ 624
2011	5,501,609	158,570,535	3.5 %	US\$ 700
2012	8,054,190	161,083,804	5.0 %	US\$ 700
2015	53,941,000	168,957,745	31.9 %	US\$ 1,080
2020	99,984,000	164,689,383	60.7 %	US\$ 1,698
2021	47,610,000	165,500,000	28.8%	US\$2458
2022	52,580,000	167,100,000	31.5%	US\$2688
2023	66,940,000	172,100,000	38.9%	US\$ 2,458

Source: BTRC 2023, GDP in USD,

Bangladesh's internet usage is maturing, with users starting with email and social networking, and then browsing for news, information, entertainment, and shopping. The country ranks 103 in the UNCTAD B2C e-commerce index report and has over 7,000 e-commerce firms, including chaldal.com, ekhanei.com, bikroy.com, rokomari.com, pickaboo.com, and daraz.com. These trends are not limited to Dhaka but also extend to semi-urban and rural areas.

About 2% of Bangladesh's population is online, with 22% of internet users shopping online and spending Tk. 7594.

The Mobile Phone subscribers are shown below:

OPERATOR	SUBSCRIBER (IN MILLIONS)
Grameen Phone Ltd. (GP)	81.45
Robi Axiata Limited (Robi)	56.35
Banglalink Digital Communications Limited	41.81
Teletalk Bangladesh Ltd. (Teletalk)	6.49
Total	186.1

Source: BTRC 2023, Subscriber in a Million

Figure 1: Mobile Phone subscribers

The total number of Internet Subscribers reached 129.40 million at the end of June 2023.

The Internet subscribers are shown below:

OPERATOR	SUBSCRIBER (MILLION)
Mobile Internet	117.25
ISP + PSTN	12.15
Total	129.40

Source: BTRC 2023, Subscriber in a Million

Figure 2: Mobile Internet & ISP+PSIN

Observing the popularity, foreign investors are coming to the Bangladeshi market, for example, recently the Chinese giant Alibaba Group bought daraz.com and books – a mobile payment system to operate in Bangladesh (Ovi, 2018). However, analyzing customer behaviors is crucial, especially in the case of online shoppers who do not get the touch and feel of the actual product during the purchase. The findings of this research may shed light on this issue.

4. THE BENEFITS OF ONLINE SHOPPING

5. THE CURRENT ONLINE SHOPPING POLICIES OF THE GOVERNMENT

Bangladesh has followed several guidelines, strategies, and movement plans to support the improvement of national e-commerce. Vision 2021 termed “Digital Bangladesh”, remains an important political driver for Bangladesh, using ICT-led development to drive socioeconomic development.

She dreams of establishing digital government services that benefit the poor and connect people through equitable access to the Internet. The government recognizes that e-commerce is prospering in Bangladesh.

The policy outlines improvement priorities inside the IT, power, and broadband sectors that allow you to support Bangladesh's development. A few key sections consist of:

- **Business to Consumers (B2C) e-commerce:** E-commerce in Bangladesh, primarily focused on B2C transactions, offers benefits such as lower operating costs, broader reach, globalization, customer convenience, and knowledge management, despite its early emergence.
- **Business to Business (B2B):** The government can develop secure B2B marketplaces and digital systems for companies, including MSMEs, through training courses or seminars. The government should focus on improving transparency in organizations and enhancing tax control systems, while also facilitating B2B transactions by addressing existing physical system issues.
- **Business to Government and Government to Business (B2G and G2B):** Bangladesh is implementing a B2G or G2B e-commerce model. This model is the way forward to create e-government, which promotes digital bidding and information services, to transition towards a digital governance system.

5.1 Legal and Regulatory Framework for E-commerce Elements of this framework include: Self-regulating

- ✓ A code of conduct should be established to ensure digital communication adheres to traditional business and social etiquette, considering the needs of both the business and the customer.
- ✓ Consumer protection laws are crucial for building consumer confidence, requiring merchants to establish a holding fund mechanism and require genuine identification for transactions.
- ✓ The confidentiality of consumer communications, preferences, access information as well as personal and financial data must be maintained by the relevant merchant.
- ✓ A clear definition of communication, intent, or promise between seller and consumer is necessary for a service agreement to be considered valid, as violations may result in legal consequences.

- ✓ Establish community policy, consider socioeconomic scenarios, and incorporate business and consumer expectations in standards. Communicate dispute resolution mechanisms and establish a cyber court for quick case resolution.

5.2 Law and Regulation/ Bangladesh Government Policy

- ✓ The IT Law is under reform, with a six-month review committee and international case studies assisting in enhancing its effectiveness in the rapidly evolving cyber world.
- ✓ E-commerce laws often combine digital actions and traditional business processes, and IT legislation must ensure compliance with applicable laws and regulations on e-commerce.
- ✓ E-commerce facilitates easy business access but requires regulation for identification, authentication, taxation, and control. A simple registration process can ensure transactions adhere to legal frameworks.
- ✓ International e-commerce requires bilateral agreements, regulatory frameworks for customs, VAT payments, rapid product release, and improved distribution channels to stimulate international business transactions.

5.3 Preserved information management

- ❖ Regular awareness and training programs should be conducted on secure information management, including data backup, integrity, authentication, and frequency of data transmission.
- ❖ Data backup and recovery are essential for e-commerce. The creation of a data center is currently underway and must be integrated.

6. MATERIALS AND METHODS

6.1 Data and Variables

This study is designed to investigate the Consumer Buying Behavior to Online Shopping of University Students in Bangladesh on the tendency of shoppers to do online shopping in Bangladesh. To understand the consumer behavior of online shopping in Bangladesh, we have undertaken a descriptive study through a survey by forming a self-constructed questionnaire considering the research objective. An open-ended and semi-structured questionnaire has been used to collect a quick response from the respondents.

This study used convenient non-probability sampling techniques to collect data from respondents in the universities around Dhaka and other divisions. Easy to use, affordable, and increasingly prevalent in IS research with considerable response rates is a handy sample strategy (Eze, Manyeki, Yaw, & Har, 2011; Ritchie, Lewis, & Ritchie, 2013; Cholls, McNaughton, & Ormiston, 2014). We have targeted 500 students from different universities and age groups with various experiences in online shopping for a personal interview, and 455 participated in the survey, resulting in a 90% response rate. However, after arranging 430 data, it would be helpful, and substantial reactions are utilized for additional examination. Ordinal Regression with link function Logit was used to demonstrate the effect on the dependent

variable based on independent variables. The data would be accumulated and analyzed through SPSS (version 22) and Microsoft Excel.

The study investigates the relationship between online shopping experiences and knowledge of information technology in Bangladesh. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data with a convenient sampling procedure. Secondary sources are also used to review relevant literature. A questionnaire was provided to university students, including bachelors and masters, to assess their satisfaction or dissatisfaction with online shopping.

7. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

7.1 Model of the study

To understand the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables, the study was attempted. The model of this study is given below:

$$CB = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AOR + \beta_2 RIR + \beta_3 SOSI + \beta_4 MPOS + \mu$$

CB = Consumer behavior

AOR = Age of Respondents

RIR = Range of Income

SOSI = Sources of Online Shopping Information

MPOS = Sources of Online Shopping Information

7.2 Select the Model

In our testing, we discovered that not all variables are significant. We found that certain factors, such as age, income range, specific sources of information for online shopping, and payment methods, have a significant influence on the outcome (Consumer behavior indicator). Conversely, we also found that some factors do not have a significant impact.

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	463.281			
Final	163.884	299.398	8	.000
Link function: Logit.				

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	173.089	37	.000
Deviance	131.433	37	.000
Link function: Logit.			

Now we fit the Ordinal Regression with the link function Logit, to demonstrate the effect on the dependent variable based on independent variables. We already selected the ordinal regression based on the goodness of fit test.

7.3 Parameter Estimates

		Estimate	Std. Error	df	Sig.(P-Value)
Location	[AOR=15-20]	-1.710	1.254	1	.172
	[AOR=21-25]	.944	.846	1	.264
	[AOR=26-30]	3.489	.985	1	.000
	[AOR=31-35]	-1.657	.838	1	.048
	[AOR=36-Above]	0 ^a	.	0	.
	[RIR=0-10,000]	-.188	.762	1	.805
	[RIR=10,000-20,000]	-2.289	.775	1	.003
	[RIR=20,000-30,000]	-1.880	.705	1	.008
	[RIR=Above 30,000]	0 ^a	.	0	.
	[SOSI=Family/friends]	-.095	.585	1	.871
	[SOSI=Others]	1.275	1.141	1	.264
	[SOSI=Promotional Campaign]	4.471	1.236	1	.000
	[SOSI=social media]	1.977	.522	1	.000
	[SOSI=Website Advertisement]	0 ^a	.	0	.
	[MPOS=]	20.005	.000	1	.
	[MPOS=Cash on Delivery]	2.395	.390	1	.000
	[MPOS=Credit card]	-1.312	.834	1	.116
	[MPOS=Debit Card]	-2.629	.568	1	.000
[MPOS=Mobile Banking]	0 ^a	.	0	.	
Link function: Logit.					
a. This parameter is set to zero because it is redundant.					

Interpretation: In this parameter estimates table, we can see the coefficients and significance levels for various factors in a logistic regression model. The results suggest the following:

Location (AOR = Age of Respondents): The statistical analysis indicates that the age group between 26-30 has a positive impact on the outcome, with an estimated value of 3.489. This result is highly statistically significant, with a p-value is less than 0.001. On the other hand, the age group between 31-35 hurts the outcome, with an estimated value of -1.657 and a statistical significance level of 0.048. This suggests a significant negative impact. The remaining age groups do not show significant differences from the reference category.

Range of Income (RIR): The income ranges of "10,000-20,000" and "20,000-30,000" have a statistically significant negative impact on the outcome compared to the reference category with p-values of 0.003 and 0.008, respectively.

Sources of Online Shopping Information (SOSI): "Promotional Campaign" and "Social Media" have positive estimates and are highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating a significant positive influence on the outcome. Other sources of information are not significantly different from the reference category.

Modes of Payment in Online Shopping (MPOS): "Cash on Delivery" has a positive estimate (2.395) and is highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), suggesting a significant positive impact on the outcome. "Credit card" and "Debit Card" have negative estimates but are not statistically significant.

Based on the logistic regression model, it can be concluded that age groups "26-30" and "31-35," specific income ranges, and sources of information such as "Promotional Campaigns" and "Social Media" play a significant role in influencing the outcome. On the other hand, variables like different categories of online shopping satisfaction and payment methods do not seem to have a significant impact. The model uses a logit link function, and some parameters are set to zero as they are deemed redundant and do not contribute significantly to the model.

7.4 The behavior of people in online shopping in Bangladesh

Table: The Overall Case Processing Summary of All Variables

Case Processing Summary			
		N	Marginal Percentage
Online shopping satisfaction	Dissatisfied	83	19.3%
	Highly Dissatisfied	2	0.5%
	Highly Satisfied	55	12.8%
	Satisfied	290	67.4%
Age of the respondents	15-20	28	6.5%
	21-25	254	59.1%
	26-30	86	20.0%
	31-35	43	10.0%
	36-Above	19	4.4%
Sources of Income of the Respondents	Business	41	9.5%
	Other Sources	49	11.4%
	Service	61	14.2%
	Student	193	44.9%
	Tuition	86	20.0%
Range of Income of the respondents	0-10,000	132	30.7%
	10,000-20,000	36	8.4%
	20,000-30,000	180	41.9%
	Above 30,000	82	19.1%
Sources of online shopping information	Family/friends	113	26.3%
	Others	23	5.3%
	Promotional Campaign	25	5.8%
	Social Media	210	48.8%
	Website Advertisement	59	13.7%
Reasons for choosing online shopping.	Available Variety	15	3.5%
	Busy Schedule	8	1.9%
	Easy to Get	99	23.0%
	Home Delivery	94	21.9%
	Saves Time	214	49.8%
Payment system security	Not Sufficient	52	12.1%
	Risky	84	19.5%
	Sufficient	294	68.4%
Modes of payment in online shopping		1	0.2%
	Cash on Delivery	293	68.1%

	Credit card	40	9.3%
	Debit Card	25	5.8%
	Mobile Banking	71	16.5%
Valid		430	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		430	

The table presents data on online shopping satisfaction and demographic variables:

Online Shopping Satisfaction: This section shows the distribution of responses for online shopping satisfaction. The majority of respondents are "Satisfied" (67.4%), followed by "Dissatisfied" (19.3%). Only a very small percentage is "Highly Dissatisfied" (0.5%) or "Highly Satisfied" (12.8%).

Age of the Respondents: It provides information about the age distribution of the respondents. The largest group falls in the "21-25" age range (59.1%), with smaller proportions in other age groups.

Sources of Income of the Respondents: This section reveals the sources of income for the respondents. The most common source is "Student" (44.9%), followed by "Service" (14.2%) and "Business" (9.5%).

Range of Income of the Respondents: It displays the income ranges of the respondents. The majority fall into the "20,000-30,000" income range (41.9%), with smaller percentages in other income categories.

Sources of Online Shopping Information: This part shows where respondents get information about online shopping. "Social Media" is the most common source (48.8%), while "Family/friends" (26.3%) and "Website Advertisement" (13.7%) are also significant sources.

Reasons for Choosing Online Shopping: It lists reasons why respondents choose online shopping. "Saves Time" is the most cited reason (49.8%), followed by "Home Delivery" (21.9%) and "Easy to Get" (23.0%).

Payment System Security: This section assesses respondents' views on payment system security. The majority find it "Sufficient" (68.4%), while some find it "Risky" (19.5%) and "Not Sufficient" (12.1%).

Modes of Payment in Online Shopping: It presents the various modes of payment used in online shopping. "Cash on Delivery" is the most common (68.1%), followed by "Mobile Banking" (16.5%) and "Credit card" (9.3%).

This summary provides an overview of respondents' distribution and characteristics, as well as their satisfaction preferences with online shopping.

a. Preference for Product/Service for Online Shopping

Figure 3: Preference for product

Comments: In this study, apparel, accessories, food, and online ticketing are the main four categories that are bringing online shopping culture among online shoppers. Online shopping tends to grow in the coming years as consumers want to buy more in the future. Merchants should bring out innovative ways so that there is growth in other categories of goods and services.

b. Factors for liking online shopping

Figure 4: Factors for online shopping

Comments: The study reveals that 202 respondents prefer online shopping due to home delivery, while 116 prefer available options. 60 prefer ease of ordering and payment gateway and 52 prefer discount offers. These findings align with previous studies by Rastogi, 2010 and Katawetawaraks and Wang, 2011.

c. Factors for Disliking Online Shopping

Figure 5: Factors disliking for online shopping

Comments: The study found that 146 respondents spoke about fraud, 107 respondents spoke about lack of commitment to service, 90 respondents spoke about our return policy, and 87 spoke about high prices. The primary barrier to online shopping is the inability to touch and trust the product, while high prices are another issue. Marketers should develop better return policies, product quality, after-sale services, and reasonable prices to encourage online shopping.

d. Modes of Payment in Online Shopping

Figure 6: Modes of Payments

Comments: The study reveals that 330 respondents prefer cash on delivery for online shopping, contrasting with 65 using mobile banking. 21 use credit cards, and 14 use debit cards. This contrast may be due to Bangladesh's less developed financial sector, where credit cards are less accessible.

e. Payment System Security

Figure 7: Payment Security

Comments: The study reveals that 263 respondents in Bangladesh believe the online shopping payment system is secure, while 96 consider it risky. 71 find the security insufficient. This raises concerns about consumer trust in online shopping, prompting companies to introduce improved technologies to boost consumer confidence.

f. Online Shopping Satisfaction

Figure 8: Online Shopping Satisfaction

Comments: The majority 340 of regular online shoppers are satisfied with their shopping experience, with only 43 being Dissatisfied 30 Highly Satisfied, and 17 highly dissatisfied. However, concerns persist, limiting frequent online shopping. Companies should address these concerns by improving information quality, and service during and post-purchase, and addressing dissatisfied and Highly Dissatisfied categories to encourage more frequent online shopping.

8. DISCUSSIONS

Among those respondents, websites, advertisements, friends, and family members are the primary sources of online shopping information for the online consumer. This result confirms the findings of Hajli (2014) and Alsubagh (2015). Time-saving, easy-to-get, home delivery, and available varieties of products are the main grounds for shopping online. All these four factors motivate an online shopper to buy over the Internet. Therefore, companies should design strategies and develop varieties of products to attract and retain online shoppers.

These findings also confirm the findings of Gong et al. (2013) and Hoque et al. (2015), where the respondents adopted e-commerce for its usefulness. 49.8% like online shopping because that saves time; 21.9% like online shopping because of home delivery facility; while about 3.5 % respondents said that available options, for this they like to shop online. These findings confirm the study of Rastogi (2010) and Katawetawaraks and Wang (2011), where online shoppers also preferred online shopping for available options, discount offers, and ease of ordering. Inability to touch and feel the product or trust is still the primary disliking factor about online shopping, or we can say the primary barrier to online shopping which confirms the study of Chen and Barnes (2007), Heijden et al. (2003) and Huseynov and Yildirim (2014).

Most of the consumers prefer cash on delivery as a mode of payment for online shopping. This finding confirms the study of Rastogi (2010) but contrasts with the findings of Liao et al. (2012), where online shoppers mostly prefer to pay through credit or debit cards. Companies should undertake measures so that dissatisfied and highly dissatisfied categories and shop online more often and it has to be done through better information quality, and quality service during purchase and post-purchase (Vegiayan et al., 2013). In the present study, we used ordinal regression analysis to measure the effect of some variables on consumer buying behavior which is agreed by George S Spais & and Konstantinos Z Vasileiou, 2006.

9. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. We found from the primary data; that online shopping is more popular among male buyers than females which is 74%. As well as Buyer's age limit is different. The majority of the respondent was 70% between 20-25 years old.
2. From this research, we got significant data about online consumers. 64% of online consumers are students and other buyers are service holders, tuition providers, businesses, and so on.

3. In this research, 75% of the interviewee's monthly income was not above ten thousand, and the other range of income ranges from 19% to 14%.
4. In this study. The rate of shopping is increasing when they become more experienced in online shopping. The majority, 49% of the respondents are shopping online occasionally and they have experience in more than four years.

For selling and promoting products online, it is essential to inform consumers about online shopping, social media is the main source of information for online shopping that were 51.50%.

5. Time-saving, easy to get, home delivery and available varieties of products are the main grounds for shopping online.
6. Most buyers prefer Apparel, accessories, food, and online ticketing are the main four categories that are bringing online shopping culture among online shoppers.
7. 47% of the respondents like online shopping because of the home delivery facility. Some of the interviewees like available options, discount offers, ease of order for buying, and payment gateway.
8. Hate the fading factor about online shopping, lack of commitment to service and products, poor return policy and high prices of products or services are the primary disliking factors about online shopping.
9. The diverse payment options for customers are an essential segment for buying decisions when doing a transaction. The Bulk of the respondents that were 81% argued about cash on delivery facility, then Mobile banking and credit & and debit cards.
10. From this study it is found that none of the respondents agree with the fact that the payment system for online shopping is highly secure in Bangladesh. 61.20% of the respondents said it is secured and some aspirants said it is risky.
11. Satisfaction level plays a significant role in online shopping. Satisfied consumers tend to shop more frequently online. After analyzing the data, we found that 81% of the respondents are satisfied with their overall online shopping experience.
12. Three benefits have been considered by online shopping. They are Social benefits, Government benefits, and future benefits. In Social benefits, one can get an electronic record of the receipt of purchase, which makes record keeping much easier, Easy to send gifts, there more variety, no crowd, and produces entrepreneurs. In government benefits, the government will earn more revenue if online shopping increases the GDP rate for the country, increases new employment opportunities, and promotes digital marketing. In the future AI and chatbots will optimize online shopping.
13. The IT Law is under reform, with a six-month review committee and international case studies assisting in enhancing its effectiveness in the rapidly evolving cyber world.

14. The statistical analysis indicates that the age group between 26-30 has a positive impact on the outcome; this result is highly statistically significant. The income ranges of "10,000-20,000" and "20,000-30,000" have a statistically significant negative impact on the outcome. "Promotional Campaigns" and "Social Media" have positive estimates and are highly statistically significant. "Cash on Delivery" has a positive estimate and is highly statistically significant. "Credit card" and "Debit Card" have negative estimates but are not statistically significant.

10. RECOMMENDATION OF THE STUDY

In this serious period of online business Bangladeshi online stores and Facebook shopping pages should keep a decent congruity with the advanced structures. A few factors that Bangladeshi online business people need to investigate are referenced underneath:

- a. Delivery of better assistance and concentrating on improved client experience ought to be expanded.
- b. The objections made by the clients ought to be going immediately to expand confidence in the shopping site.
- c. Plans should be created to recognize different components that influence clients' fulfillment.
- d. Since internet shopping is another division of Bangladesh before going into the opposition client's necessity must be explored.
- e. The online protection and well-being rules ought to be kept up by the Cyber Security Act.
- f. There ought to consistently be twofold checking to guarantee mistake-free items go to clients.
- g. Bangladesh has heightened suspicion towards online shopping due to recent scandals, including payments without deliveries. The Bangladesh Bank has stopped processing payments without deliveries, and the government's pressure to reduce fraud and increase transparency has led to landlords' and banks' reluctance to rent space to e-commerce companies.
- h. More inclined to cite substance ought to be given so clients have an away from the item they will get.
- i. Lag time will be reduced.
- j. Regulatory authority should Establish community policy, consider socioeconomic scenarios, and incorporate business and consumer expectations in standards.
- k. E-commerce facilitates easy business access but should establish regulations for identification, authentication, taxation, and control.

- l. International e-commerce should incorporate bilateral agreements, regulatory frameworks for customs, VAT payments, rapid product release, and improved distribution channels to stimulate international business transactions.
- m. Online shopping strategies should be focused on age groups "26-30" and "31-35," specific income ranges and advanced strategy should be promoted on "Promotional Campaign" and "Social Media". In addition to cash on delivery, another prompt payment method should be introduced such as Bkash, Nogod, or another online cash payment method.

11. CONCLUSION

Earlier studies showed that in contrast to brick-and-mortar-looking behavior, online-looking behavior is influenced by internet property, website esthetics Constantinides, 2004, security, customers' expertise, age and learning curve, etc. finding out these distinctive characteristics of online shopping and shopper behavior of internet buyers would profit the tech-entrepreneurs and policymakers to craft their ways properly for the market. This study, through empirical observation, reveals the patron behavior of internet buyers in Bangladesh. They are doing online shopping as a result of it saving time, offering home delivery, providing ease of looking, and offering an additional kind of product for apparel, accessories, and ticketing than that of brick-and-mortar stores. The study might not have been able to reach every student who lives in Dhaka and other part of the country. This study does not categorize all students and it has time constraints. In this study, the respondents are not equally concerned about the survey and many factors such as web design, quality, services, and ethics have not been considered.

They largely believe in worth and their expertise as the basis of the standard judgment of things online and for payment systems they like money on delivery possibility. Most of the patrons get the knowledge primarily from Facebook advertisements that are pursued by friends and family by following their "word of mouth" communication. However, privacy and inability to the touch and feel are the foremost disliking factors for internet buyers. In the future policy policymakers can introduce different online payment methods to encourage customers.

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